

A Hierarchical Framework for the Management of Carpooling Using Autonomous Vehicles

Abstract—The growing diffusion of Autonomous Vehicles (AVs) is reshaping urban mobility by enabling new forms of intelligent transportation, such as shared and on-demand services. Among these, carpooling with AVs represents a promising solution to reduce traffic congestion, emissions, and operational costs. However, optimizing shared rides in real-time urban environments remains a complex challenge due to dynamic traffic conditions and the need for efficient routing.

This paper presents a hierarchical framework for carpooling management based on two strategies: i) the Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) to optimize the sequence of pick-ups and drop-off operations performed by AVs, ii) a rerouting algorithm for selecting the best route considering traffic conditions. To this aim, the carpooling problem is formalized using the Markov Decision Process framework. The approach is implemented using the Proximal Policy Optimization algorithm and validated through simulations conducted by the Simulation of Urban Mobility tool.

As a case study, the cities of Bari (Italy) and Tampere (Finland) are analyzed to assess the model performance in real urban scenarios. The results demonstrate the potential of the proposed method to improve route efficiency, reduce travel time and emissions, and support the development of intelligent and sustainable mobility systems.

Note to Practitioners—This work proposes a hierarchical framework including a Deep Reinforcement Learning strategy and an optimization algorithm to provide practical solutions for deploying intelligent shared mobility with autonomous vehicles. In particular, a novel real-time car pooling management approach solves the complex problem of optimal scheduling pick-up and drop-off operations of users. The proposed framework will be of basic importance for public authorities and traffic stakeholders to renew intelligent mobility on the basis of shared vehicles. The societal impact will be the alleviation of congestion and pollution thanks to the vehicle sharing, and the increase of safety and inclusiveness thanks to the use of autonomous vehicles.

Index Terms—Deep Reinforcement Learning, Autonomous Vehicles, Carpooling, Simulation

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid advancement of AVs is reshaping the landscape of modern mobility and transportation. AVs, designed to operate without human intervention, leverage a sophisticated combination of sensors, Artificial Intelligence (AI), and Machine Learning (ML) algorithms to perceive their environment, make decisions, and navigate autonomously. These capabilities promise significant improvements in road safety, traffic efficiency, and environmental sustainability. One of the most compelling benefits of AVs is the substantial reduction in road accidents, as human errors such as distractions, fatigue, and impulsive decision-making account for a majority of crashes [1]. AVs, equipped with suitable driving algorithms and real-time monitoring systems, mitigate these risks, offering safer roadways [2].

Beyond safety, AVs contribute to improve traffic management by enabling more efficient vehicle coordination, reducing

congestion, and optimizing transportation networks [3]. Studies in mixed-traffic environments suggest that even moderate adoption of AVs can lead to a significant improvement in traffic flow, while higher adoption rates produce more complex dynamics [4]. Furthermore, intelligent driving strategies such as Model Predictive Control (MPC) allow AVs to optimize navigation in urban and suburban environments by adjusting acceleration and steering in real time [3]. Similarly, eco-driving techniques, which enable AVs to adapt their behavior based on traffic signals and surrounding vehicles, have demonstrated potential in reducing energy consumption and improving overall driving efficiency [5].

However, the effective deployment of AVs requires advanced planning methodologies to handle complex urban environments characterized by unpredictable traffic conditions, congested intersections, and varying road structures. A critical aspect of AV functionality is trajectory and route planning, which ensures that AVs can navigate safely and efficiently. Various techniques have been explored to optimize this process, including Reinforcement Learning (RL)-based approaches [6], heuristic algorithms such as ant colony optimization [7], and the Multi-layer Grid Neighborhood A* algorithm [8]. Furthermore, emerging blockchain-based solutions have been proposed to improve the security and transparency of autonomous mobility systems, mitigate cyber threats, and ensure data integrity [9].

Within the broader domain of AVs, one particularly promising application is carpooling or ride-sharing, which aims to reduce the number of vehicles on the road by allowing multiple passengers to share a ride. This strategy aligns well with the capabilities of AVs, as autonomous ride-sharing services can dynamically adjust routes, optimize pick-up and drop-off sequences, and minimize travel times [10]. To better understand the operational setting of this problem, Fig. 1 provides a schematic representation of a typical carpooling scenario. In this setting, an AV is tasked with serving multiple passengers by efficiently managing a sequence of pick-up and drop-off requests across a road network. The goal is to minimize total mission time and improve system-wide efficiency by leveraging real-time information and advanced decision-making policies. AI-powered frameworks such as *RouteSense* utilize ML to refine carpooling routes based on historical travel data and user preferences [11]. Additionally, decentralized ride-sharing platforms like *Cabverse* leverage blockchain technology to enhance transparency and security, addressing common challenges associated with centralized ride-hailing services [12].

This paper proposes a hierarchical framework based on a DRL approach to optimize AV carpooling operations coupled with a rerouting algorithm to compute the optimal paths for

Fig. 1. Representation of a generic carpooling problem.

the AV during a mission. Unlike recent literature that relies on heuristic or static optimization methods such as Car4Pac [10], this article introduces an optimal decision-making model that AVs can implement in real time to improve efficiency and adaptability in ride-sharing scenarios.

The main contributions of this work are enlightened in the following.

- **A Hierarchical Framework:** The proposed approach operates at two hierarchical levels to dynamically optimize carpooling decisions and AV routes.
- **Passenger Scheduling:** At the first level, the decision process is modeled as a Markov Decision Process (MDP). To face the complexity of the system in large environments, such as large cities, a DRL model determines step by step the optimal sequence of passenger pick-ups and drop-offs.
- **Route Optimization:** Once the next pick-up or drop-off target is established, the second management level applies an optimal route planning algorithm that takes into account real-time traffic conditions and congestion patterns to compute the shortest feasible route to the next location.
- **Real-World Validation:** The effectiveness of the approach and the training of the DRL agent is demonstrated through simulations performed in the Simulation of Urban Mobility (SUMO) tool in real-world urban environments, specifically in the Hervanta district of Tampere (Finland) and the city of Bari (Italy).

Hence, combining DRL for high-level decision-making with a routing algorithm for route optimization, this framework ensures adaptability and computational efficiency compared to traditional carpooling models. As a result, this paper provides a valuable contribution to the advancement of intelligent mobility solutions through ML-driven carpooling optimization.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II discusses existing research in autonomous driving, route planning and carpooling technologies; Section III introduces the fundamental aspects of the carpooling problem; Section IV details the proposed approach by specifying the DRL for optimizing carpooling with AVs; Section V presents the case study and the simulation results to validate the effectiveness of the proposed method, and Section VI summarizes key findings and discusses potential future research directions.

II. RELATED WORKS

The field of AVs has been extensively studied, addressing various challenges and opportunities to improve reliability, safety, and efficiency. One of the key aspects influencing route selection in AVs is the consideration of safety and comfort, ensuring optimal paths that adapt to road conditions and automation levels [21]. Researchers have developed models that prioritize the passenger experience by incorporating factors such as road quality, traffic congestion, and accident-prone zones. These efforts aim to improve not only the efficiency of AV navigation, but also the overall passenger experience, making autonomous driving safer and more comfortable.

A critical concern in the adoption of AVs is forensic analysis in accident scenarios, which introduces complexities in determining liability and fault attribution. Traditional forensic techniques often prove inadequate due to the sophisticated interplay of hardware, software, and external environmental factors in AV incidents. To address these challenges, researchers have developed innovative methodologies to analyze sensor data, vehicle logs, and environmental factors [1]. These approaches enable accurate incident reconstruction, aiding both legal and insurance assessments. Additionally, forensic frameworks leveraging AI-based analytics enhance the precision of accident causality determination, providing robust insights into system failures and driver interactions.

In addition to forensic analysis, ensuring the safety and reliability of AVs involves extensive virtual testing. Researchers use simulation environments to replicate various road conditions and scenarios, allowing the refinement of control algorithms without the high costs associated with field tests [2]. These virtual tests are crucial for identifying potential issues and improving the robustness of AV systems before deployment in real-world conditions.

In the field of predictive navigation, MPC has proven to be an effective method for precise vehicle navigation. MPC utilizes onboard sensors to continuously monitor and adjust steering and acceleration, ensuring optimal performance in various environments, particularly urban and suburban [3]. This technique enables AVs to navigate complex road networks, handle dynamic obstacles, and maintain smooth and efficient driving patterns.

For environmental sustainability, eco-driving strategies enhance the capabilities of AVs by optimizing energy efficiency and reducing emissions. By enabling AVs to adapt their behavior based on traffic signals and surrounding vehicles, these strategies lead to significant improvements in energy consumption and driving comfort [5]. Intelligent driving systems can dynamically adjust speed and acceleration to minimize fuel consumption and reduce greenhouse gas emissions, contributing to more sustainable urban mobility.

ML techniques have significantly contributed to enhance AV capabilities. By leveraging data-driven models, AVs can predict and adapt to dynamic traffic conditions. Advanced ML techniques have been applied to vehicle trajectory prediction, improving decision-making in connected vehicle environments and reducing collision risks [26]. Additionally, predictive maintenance approaches utilizing ML algorithms

enable proactive identification of potential component failures, reducing vehicle downtime and maintenance expenses [28]. Moreover, Deep Neural Networks (DNN) have been employed to optimize the testing and validation of Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS), ensuring efficient and high-quality performance evaluations in both laboratory and real-world scenarios [24].

Path planning, a fundamental component of AVs, has also benefited from ML advancements. Traditional path planning algorithms struggle with real-time adaptability and dynamic road conditions. In response, DRL-based approaches have led to optimized path planning methodologies capable of efficiently navigating complex traffic environments [27]. Furthermore, dynamic path planning frameworks incorporating Deep Learning (DL) techniques enhance AV decision-making by continuously adapting to real-time traffic data [14]. The integration of DRL with the Rapidly-exploring Random Tree algorithm has further improved exploration efficiency and route optimization [15]. Similarly, DRL-based approaches have demonstrated remarkable adaptability in heterogeneous and unpredictable driving conditions, enhancing safety and efficiency [16].

In addition to ML-driven methodologies, heuristic and algorithmic techniques have been explored to enhance AV route optimization. Potential field models assess driving risks to determine safer trajectories by evaluating potential collision zones, road curvature, and sudden obstacle appearances [17]. Heuristic methods, such as optimized ant colony algorithms, have been applied to ride-hailing services, significantly reducing travel costs and optimizing shared mobility [7]. The Multi-layer Grid Neighborhood A* algorithm further refines path planning by minimizing steering angles and enhancing navigation accuracy, particularly in dense urban environments [8].

The integration of AVs with urban mobility solutions has been a focal point of research aimed at improving traffic efficiency and reducing congestion. Real-time path planning systems leverage statistical models to enhance travel time predictions, benefiting smart city applications and intelligent transportation systems [22].

Moreover, efforts to increase software flexibility have led to the development of hardware-agnostic interfaces between path planning and trajectory planning systems, improving the re-usability of autonomous driving frameworks [18]. This approach allows AV systems to be more adaptable and easier to integrate with different hardware platforms.

Furthermore, Global Positioning System data and advanced traffic analysis techniques have facilitated cost-effective and timely routing solutions, even in scenarios with incomplete data availability [19]. By leveraging real-world vehicle movement data, solutions such as *Car4Pac* have improved last-mile delivery efficiency through route-sharing mechanisms, enabling faster and more sustainable urban logistics [10].

The evolution of carpooling and ride-sharing systems has further transformed urban mobility paradigms. RL-based methods dynamically adapt to fluctuating traffic conditions, optimizing real-time driving strategies [6]. Studies on one-way car-sharing systems indicate that ride-sharing can enhance op-

erational efficiency, significantly reducing vehicle kilometers traveled and environmental impact [23]. Additionally, ML-driven intelligent carpooling systems, such as those employing genetic algorithms, have improved route optimization and passenger matching efficiency [13]. Personalized ride-sharing experiences have also been improved by natural language processing classification models, which match users based on social compatibility [25].

Finally, AI and blockchain technologies are revolutionizing carpooling services by improving security, efficiency, and trust. *RouteSense* solution employs ML algorithms to optimize carpooling routes based on historical travel data and user preferences, ensuring cost-effective and convenient shared transportation [11]. Meanwhile, decentralized ride-sharing platforms such as *Cabverse* system utilize blockchain technology to enhance transaction transparency and security, addressing privacy concerns and trust issues associated with centralized ride-hailing services [12].

These advancements collectively underscore the multidisciplinary nature of AV research, which spans various fields such as forensic analysis, ML-based path planning, heuristic optimization, smart mobility integration, and the use of blockchain in ride-sharing systems. A key aspect of these innovations is the importance of carpooling, which significantly contributes to reducing traffic, transportation costs, and environmental impact. The convergence of these technologies is not only increasing the safety and efficiency of autonomous vehicles but also promoting more sustainable mobility solutions. The interaction of these developments will continue to shape the future of autonomous transportation, making the mobility system safer, more efficient, and accessible on a global scale.

In contrast to most existing works that adopt heuristic algorithms for ride-sharing and carpooling, this paper leverages a hierarchical architecture with DRL to optimize both pick-up/drop-off scheduling and routing decisions.

III. PRELIMINARIES

A. Carpooling Problem

Let us consider the set of m passengers $U = \{u_i | i = 1, 2, \dots, m\}$ in a city who need to use the carpooling service operated by an AV. The road network of the considered area is modeled as a graph $G(J, E)$ where the set of nodes $J = \{j_1, j_2, \dots, j_n, \dots, j_{|J|}\}$ is the set of junctions or intersections and the set of edges $E = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_{|E|}\}$ is the set of the roads. Note that symbol $|A|$ denotes the cardinality of the generic set A . Moreover, it holds that an edge $e = (j, r) \in E$ if there exists a road starting from $j \in J$ and ending in $r \in J$.

In detail, for a generic mission, each passenger $u_i \in U$ requests to be picked up at edge $p_i \in E$ and to be dropped at edge $d_i \in E$. In that respect, it is assumed that a AV is able to transport m passengers concurrently. The AV is also required to collect all requests from the m passengers before starting the mission and to minimize the waiting and the travel times.

Now, let us define the AV mission as the ordered set $M = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_i, \dots, p_m, d_1, d_2, \dots, d_i, \dots, d_m\}$, where p_i and d_i represent the pick-up and drop edges of the i -th passenger, respectively. In the initial configuration, the AV

picks up all passengers in sequence and takes them to their final destination in the same order. However, there are $2m!$ possible permutations of the set M in which the actions are arranged in a different order. Let us define the following function that associates to each element of M its position in the mission:

$$\mathcal{I} : M \rightarrow \mathfrak{S},$$

where \mathfrak{S} is the set of positive integer numbers. Hence, since a passenger must be first picked up and then it is released, a permutation is feasible if $\mathcal{I}(p_i) < \mathcal{I}(d_i) \quad \forall i = 1, \dots, m$. Then, we denote by $\mathbf{M}_f = \{M_j | j = 1, 2, \dots, |\mathbf{M}_f|\}$ the set collecting the missions with feasible permutations of the elements in M .

The objective of the carpooling problem is to select the permutation $M_j \in \mathbf{M}_f$ that minimizes the total mission time. The solution depends not only on the sequence M_j , but also on the path the AV has to follow on the graph G to visit all pick-up and drop edges.

B. Markov Decision Process Formulation

To solve the carpooling problem, the mission is first modeled as an MDP denoted by the 5-tuple $MDP = (\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{A}, P, R, \gamma)$ where \mathcal{S} is the state space, \mathcal{A} is the set of possible actions, P is the probability distribution of the next state given the current state and action, R is the reward function, and γ is a discount factor.

In the proposed model, the AV, which is the agent, at each time step t , after observing the current state $s_t \in \mathcal{S}$, decides the next pick-up or drop-off target by taking action $a_t \in \mathcal{A}$. As a result, a new state s_{t+1} is observed. Then, the AV receives a fixed penalty, i.e. a negative reward, for each elapsed step before completing the mission and an additional higher penalty if an infeasible action has been selected. The procedure is repeated until the AV drops the last passenger and terminates the mission.

More in detail, at each time step t , the state s_t is defined as follows:

$$s_t = \{\hat{e}, \lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_i, \dots, \lambda_m\} \quad (1)$$

where $\hat{e} \in E$ and λ_i are the locations of the AV and the state of passenger $u_i \in U$ at time step t respectively. Here, λ_i is denoted as follows:

$$\lambda_i = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } u_i \text{ has not been picked up} \\ 1 & \text{if } u_i \text{ has been picked up} \\ 2 & \text{if } u_i \text{ has been dropped off.} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Recalling the definition of the AV mission M , the action space \mathcal{A} is made by the pick-up and drop-off actions associated to the passengers and is denoted by:

$$\mathcal{A} = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_i, \dots, p_m, d_1, d_2, \dots, d_i, \dots, d_m\}. \quad (3)$$

At each time t , a single action $a_t \in \mathcal{A}$ is selected by the agent as the next pick-up or drop target.

In addition, the reward r_t at each time step t is defined as follows:

$$r_t = r_1 + r_2 \quad (4)$$

$$\text{where } r_1 = -1, \quad (4a)$$

$$r_2 = \begin{cases} -\mu & \text{if } a_t \text{ is infeasible,} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (4b)$$

r_1 increments the elapsed mission time at each time step, and r_2 assigns a further penalty μ if the action a_t selected by the AV agent at time step t is infeasible.

It is evident that the size of the state space \mathcal{S} and the action space \mathcal{A} depend on the size of the sets E and U . As a consequence, when the considered city area is large, E collects hundreds or thousands roads and the number of users is high, the dimension of the MDP model is too large and can not be solved by a traditional approach. To address such an issue a DRL approach coupled with a rerouting algorithm is used.

IV. THE HIERARCHICAL FRAMEWORK

In this section we propose a two-step hierarchical approach to solve the carpooling problem based on a DRL scheme for selecting the feasible mission and an optimization rerouting algorithm to minimize the AV route.

Fig. 2. The operational flow of an AV agent: at each time step the agent receives a state and a reward from the environment, which is simulated using the SUMO platform; based on this information, the agent takes an action which is processed through an inner rerouting module to optimize navigation. The environment updates the new state and provides a corresponding reward, completing the RL feedback loop.

The proposed hierarchical framework is depicted in Fig. 2 that shows the operational flow of the agent AV. In detail, an outer DRL scheme implements the MDP: the environment is an urban traffic simulation provided by SUMO and the agent is an AV operating the carpooling service in the simulation.

At each time step t , for the state s_t , the current edge \hat{e} is evaluated by observing the AV location in SUMO. Moreover, the agent keeps track of the state λ_i of the i^{th} passenger and takes the pick-up or drop action a_t . Subsequently, the action a_t is plugged in an inner rerouting algorithm that calculates the best route to the next pick-up or drop-off location. The path is then returned to the SUMO environment that takes the AV to the next destination. After performing the pick-up or drop-off action, the process restarts and iterates itself until the end of the mission.

A. DRL Based Pick-up and Drop-off Operations

The efficient management of pick-up and drop-off operations is essential for optimizing autonomous carpooling services. The goal is to minimize total mission time, reduce passenger waiting times, and improve overall route efficiency. The DRL agent plays a crucial role in the decision-making process, as it enables the agent to learn optimal pick-up and drop-off sequences.

Although the action space modeled in Section III-B is discrete and finite, the high dimension of the state space resulting from the number of passengers and the complexity of the road network leads to a combinatorial explosion in the size of the set $\mathcal{S} \times \mathcal{A}$. In this context, an Actor-Critic DRL framework [30] provides an effective solution, as it allows direct learning of the policy with faster convergence and better stability.

B. Actor-Critic Approach

The Actor-Critic framework belongs to the class of policy-based reinforcement learning methods and is characterized by a dual architecture, consisting of two interconnected neural networks: an *actor* and a *critic*. The separation into two networks is essential because it allows the algorithm to simultaneously learn a policy and evaluate its quality. Specifically, the actor learns the policy $\pi_\theta(a|s)$ that maps states to actions, while the critic estimates the value function $V_w(s)$ or the advantage function $A(s, a)$ to assess the quality of actions taken by the actor [30].

This dual structure facilitates an effective balance between *exploration* and *exploitation*. At the initial stages of learning, the stochastic nature of the actor's policy promotes exploration, allowing the agent to try a diverse set of actions and gather sufficient information about the environment. As training progresses and the critic provides increasingly accurate value estimates, the policy gradually shifts toward exploitation, favoring actions that yield higher expected returns. This transition is crucial to avoid suboptimal policies caused by premature convergence and ensures stable learning even in complex, dynamic environments like the pick-up and drop-off management in carpooling systems.

In our work, we adopt the Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) algorithm [31], a modern actor-critic method that further stabilizes training by employing clipped surrogate objectives, preventing overly large and destabilizing policy updates.

In the following the actor-critic method is described in detail.

- **Actor:** A neural network is responsible for learning the policy $\pi_\theta(a|s)$, mapping states to a probability distribution over actions and selecting actions accordingly.
- **Critic:** A second neural network approximates the value function $V_w(s)$, providing feedback on the quality of the actions taken to guide and stabilize the actor's learning process.

The learning process relies on the *Advantage Function* A_t , which quantifies how much better (or worse) a particular action

was compared to the expected average performance from the same state:

$$A_t = r_t + \gamma V_w(s_{t+1}) - V_w(s_t),$$

where:

- A_t is the advantage at time step t ;
- r_t is the immediate reward received after taking action a_t in state s_t ;
- γ is the discount factor ($0 < \gamma \leq 1$), which controls the importance of future rewards;
- $V_w(s_{t+1})$ is the estimated value of the next state, as predicted by the critic;
- $V_w(s_t)$ is the estimated value of the current state.

Using A_t , the policy parameters θ are updated by performing gradient ascent on the expected return:

$$\nabla_\theta J(\theta) = \mathbb{E}_{\pi_\theta} [\nabla_\theta \log \pi_\theta(a_t|s_t) \cdot A_t],$$

where:

- $\nabla_\theta J(\theta)$ is the gradient of the expected return with respect to the policy parameters;
- $\log \pi_\theta(a_t|s_t)$ is the logarithm of the probability of taking action a_t in state s_t under the current policy;

At the same time, the critic parameters w are updated to minimize the Temporal-Difference (TD) error which measures the difference between the predicted value and the target value:

$$L(w) = (r_t + \gamma V_w(s_{t+1}) - V_w(s_t))^2,$$

where:

- $L(w)$ is the loss function for the critic;

C. Policy Optimization

In the proposed implementation, the PPO algorithm is adopted using a clipped surrogate objective [31] that constrains the deviation between the new and old policies, and avoids destructive policy updates. In more detail, the following loss function is used during the training:

$$L^{\text{PPO}}(\theta) = \mathbb{E}_t [\min(r_t(\theta)A_t, \text{clip}(r_t(\theta), 1 - \epsilon, 1 + \epsilon)A_t)],$$

where:

- $L^{\text{PPO}}(\theta)$ is the surrogate loss function used to update the policy;
- $r_t(\theta) = \frac{\pi_\theta(a_t|s_t)}{\pi_{\theta_{\text{old}}}(a_t|s_t)}$ is the ratio between the probability of taking action a_t under the new policy versus the old policy;
- ϵ is a small positive hyperparameter that limits how much the policy is allowed to change;
- $\text{clip}(r_t(\theta), 1 - \epsilon, 1 + \epsilon)$ ensures that the ratio stays within the safe range to prevent large policy updates.

This clipped surrogate objective ensures that policy updates are conservative, enhancing training stability which is an essential feature in complex environments. In this work, the Actor-Critic approach, and in particular the PPO, provides the right trade-off between expressiveness and stability and allows the carpooling controller to learn complex pick-up and drop-off policies in a scalable and data-efficient manner.

D. Rerouting Algorithm

After each decision step, the rerouting mechanism is systematically invoked to recompute the optimal path toward the next pick-up or drop-off point. This continuous recalculation allows the system to adapt in real time to changing traffic conditions or unexpected events. By updating the route, the framework ensures that autonomous vehicles follow the most efficient trajectories, minimizing overall travel time. The rerouting process leverages updated state information from the environment, such as vehicle positions and traffic flow, to refine the planned itinerary and support more effective ride-sharing operations.

The rerouting process consists of the following sequential steps:

- 1) **Reevaluation of Optimal Path:** When a rerouting trigger is detected, an alternative path is computed using a *rerouting algorithm* that incorporates real-time weight adjustments for traffic conditions.
- 2) **Execution of New Route:** The vehicle updates its navigation system and follows the revised path, ensuring that road disruptions are handled efficiently without compromising passenger service.

As it is enlightened by the related literature [29], through extensive simulations, the rerouting mechanism has shown significant improvements in key performance metrics:

- **reduction in Travel Time:** by dynamically avoiding congestion, the algorithm reduces unnecessary delays and ensures faster service;
- **improved energy efficiency:** the adaptive rerouting minimizes idle time and unnecessary travel, leading to lower energy consumption.

To highlight the advantages of the proposed rerouting system, Table I presents a comparison between static route planning and adaptive rerouting.

TABLE I
COMPARISON BETWEEN STATIC AND ADAPTIVE REROUTING APPROACHES

Feature	Static Routing	Adaptive Rerouting
Traffic Handling	Fixed, no updates	Dynamic, real-time adjustments
Energy Efficiency	Suboptimal due to fixed routes	Optimized based on conditions

V. CASE STUDY

In this section the proposed hierarchical approach is applied to optimize autonomous carpooling in two urban case studies: Bari (Italy) and Tampere (Finland). Moreover, the section describes the environment configuration, algorithm implementation, performance metrics, training phase, simulation results and the comparison between the two implemented scenarios and a baseline taxi scenario.

We use OpenStreetMap (OSM) for the geographical map construction and the SUMO framework for traffic simulations to provide a robust foundation for evaluating the algorithm’s capabilities in real-world settings. The geographical maps of

Tampere and Bari are represented respectively in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4.

Fig. 3. The simulation environment of the Hervanta neighborhood in Tampere (Finland). The area is characterized by a combination of urban and suburban roads.

Fig. 4. The urban environment of Bari (Italy), which represents a denser and more complex scenario with respect to Tampere scenario. The road network features a high density of intersections, traffic lights, and limited-access areas.

A. Environment Setup

In Bari, the complex and irregular infrastructure, characterized by narrow streets and historical architecture, poses unique challenges for autonomous carpooling. The DRL algorithm ability to adapt to these conditions and optimize the sequence of pick-up and drop-off points is crucial for efficient navigation. The Automatic Routing [33] feature provided by SUMO ensures that the route with least travel time between these points is computed, further enhancing the overall performance.

In Tampere, the suburban environment with a regular road network and well-planned infrastructure provides a controlled setting to test the hierarchical DRL approach. The DRL algorithm efficiently optimizes the sequence of pick-up and drop-off points, while SUMO Automatic Routing [33] minimizes the travel distances between these points, demonstrating the model effectiveness in a less congested and more structured urban environment as in Bari Scenario.

The implementation is developed in Python using TensorFlow (for DL), NumPy (for data processing), and Matplotlib (for visualization). Visual Studio Code (VSC) serves as the development environment. OSM data is converted to SUMO compatible formats to generate accurate road networks. Ray

RLlib [32] is used to manage DRL experiments, and Matlab is used for post-simulation performance analysis. The PPO algorithm is chosen to train the agent’s decision-making policy within a hierarchical framework.

B. Implementation Details

The simulation runs in a Python 3.7.15 Anaconda environment. The required libraries, including TensorFlow, SUMO, Gym, and Ray RLLib, are installed using `pip`.

The implementation process includes the following operations.

- 1) **Map Extraction:** OSM data for Tampere and Bari are processed, cleaned and converted to SUMO networks with detailed intersection and road configurations.
- 2) **Map Refinement:** Issues such as disconnected roads or incorrect traffic elements are corrected through manual adjustments and automated scripts to ensure realistic traffic flow.
- 3) **Agent Training:** The agent is trained independently for each scenario using hierarchical approach.
- 4) **Performance Evaluation:** After training, the agent performance is assessed using quantitative metrics, followed by data analysis and visualization in Matlab.

The DRL model is trained using the PPO algorithm with the configuration described in the following:

- **Episodes:** 20,000 episodes for each environment.
- **Reward calculation:** Negative r_t for time spent and errors in decision-making.
- **Time Penalty:** A penalty $r_1 = -1$ is applied for each time step to encourage faster task completion.
- **Invalid Action Penalty:** A penalty $\mu = -10$ is applied if the agent attempts to pick-up or drop-off a passenger already processed.
- **Exploration-Exploitation Balance:** Managed through adaptive policies to prevent premature convergence.

The algorithm’s effectiveness is assessed using the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) reported in Table II.

TABLE II
PERFORMANCE METRICS FOR DRL EVALUATION

KPI	Description
Average Reward	Cumulative reward achieved per episode
Mission Time	Time required to complete the task
Error Rate	Number of suboptimal decisions made by the agent
Emission Comparison	Total Product Pollution

C. Simulation Results

The proposed DRL-based carpooling algorithm is extensively tested to optimize the pick-up and drop-off times for five passengers. The simulation environment is designed to evaluate the algorithm performance without considering real-time traffic data. This setup focuses on assessing the agent ability to optimize passenger transport under idealized conditions, without the added complexity of traffic variability.

The metrics of interest show the results listed in the following.

- **Reward Convergence:** The average increase over the course of training, indicating that the algorithm is learning to optimize its decisions effectively. For the city of Tampere as shown in Fig. 5, the reward stabilizes at approximately -300, while for Bari as shown in Fig. 6, it stabilizes at around -350. This difference suggests that the algorithm may have encountered slightly more challenging conditions in Bari, or that the urban layout of Bari required more complex decision-making. Initially, the average reward for Bari was around -2600, indicating a series of suboptimal actions. However, over the epochs, a gradual improvement was observed, with the reward stabilizing around -350, similar to Tampere.
- **Error Reduction:** The number of errors per episode dropped significantly during training, stabilizing below 50 in Tampere as shown in Fig. 7 and below 30 in Bari as shown in Fig. 8. This trend demonstrates that the algorithm’s decision-making accuracy improved over time, leading to fewer mistakes in passenger transport. Initially, the number of errors per episode was quite high, suggesting frequent mistakes and non-optimal actions. However, as training progressed, a decreasing trend in the average number of errors is observed, indicating improved decision-making and more effective behaviors.
- **Mission Time Optimization:** The histogram in Fig. 9 provides a clear comparison of mission time distributions between Bari and Tampere. In Bari, the mission time distribution is centered around 900 seconds, while in Tampere it is centered around 1000 seconds. The Tampere distribution shows a sharper peak, indicating that a large number of episodes consistently achieved mission times close to this value. Similarly, Bari shows a slightly wider but still concentrated distribution. This concentration of episodes within a narrow time range suggests that the agent has successfully learned an efficient policy: the training process has led to stable and optimized mission durations.

Fig. 5. Average Reward Trend in Tampere

Fig. 8. Error Reduction per Episode in Bari

Fig. 6. Average Reward Trend in Bari

Fig. 9. Histogram comparison of mission time distributions for the Bari (green) and Tampere (blue) scenarios: highlighted bins in darker shades represent convergence values, i.e., the most frequent mission durations where the agent behavior stabilizes; the remaining bins (lighter shades) correspond to training-phase variability.

Fig. 7. Error Reduction per Episode in Tampere

D. Fuel Emission Comparison: CarPooling vs Baseline Taxi Scenario

To quantitatively evaluate the environmental impact of the proposed hierarchical carpooling management system, a comparative study on fuel emissions is conducted. This analysis focuses on three types of emissions: CO₂ (carbon dioxide), NO₂ (nitrogen dioxide), and PM_x (particulate matter), which are among the most relevant indicators in urban mobility assessments.

A total of 100 episodes are evaluated for each scenario (carpooling with DRL and Baseline Taxi), considering the agent already trained in the carpooling setting. The goal is to assess how the optimized route planning and passenger grouping in carpooling scenarios affect emissions compared to a sequential pick-up/drop-off strategy typical of conventional taxis.

The comparison is summarized in the following.

- **Carpooling with DRL:** The agent optimizes multiple pick-up and drop-off points in a single trip by applying hierarchical decision-making, reducing redundant routing and increasing vehicle occupancy.

- **Baseline Taxi:** Each passenger is served individually in a point-to-point trip, resulting in increased travel distance and lower route efficiency due to the absence of coordinated ride sharing.

a) *CO₂ Emissions:*

- In the DRL-based carpooling scenario, values ranged between 4000 mg and 7000 mg, with a mean emission of 5300 mg.
- In the baseline taxi scenario, values ranged between 5000 mg and 10000 mg, with a higher mean of 7800 mg.

As shown in Fig. 10, the carpooling scenario exhibits a lower and more compact distribution of CO₂ emissions compared to the traditional taxi scenario. This reduction highlights the effectiveness of the autonomous vehicle’s ability to intelligently determine the sequence of pick-up and drop-off points. Through training, the system learns to optimize routing in a way that minimizes the total distance traveled and overall travel time, which in turn leads to a significant decrease in CO₂ emissions.

Fig. 10. CO₂ Emissions per Episode: carpooling vs baseline taxi scenario

b) *NO₂ Emissions:*

- DRL-Carpooling episodes recorded values between 2 mg and 3 mg, averaging 2.55 mg.
- In contrast, the baseline scenario produced emissions between 3 mg and 4.5 mg, with an average of 3.4 mg.

Fig. 11 confirms a consistent reduction in NO₂ levels with DRL-enabled shared mobility. This outcome is particularly significant given that NO₂ emissions are closely linked to vehicle idling and frequent acceleration cycles—conditions that are substantially reduced thanks to the shorter overall trip durations enabled by DRL-based carpooling optimization.

Fig. 11. NO₂ Emissions per Episode: carpooling vs baseline taxi scenario

c) *PM_x Emissions:*

- Carpooling episodes generated PM_x emissions in the range of 0.1 mg to 0.25 mg, with an average of 0.16 mg.
- Taxi episodes exhibited higher values between 0.15 mg and 0.45 mg, with a mean of 0.29 mg.

As shown in Fig. 12, PM_x emissions are substantially lower in the carpooling configuration, which benefits from smoother route allocation and fewer trip initiations per passenger, reducing acceleration/deceleration peaks typically associated with particulate emissions. This reduction is further supported by the decreased overall travel time made possible through DRL-based carpooling, which limits the frequency and intensity of driving patterns that generate particulate matter.

Fig. 12. PM_x Emissions per Episode: carpooling vs baseline taxi scenario

E. Discussion

The DRL-based approach proved to be highly effective in optimizing routing and reducing both waiting times and unnecessary stops. By leveraging real-time data in combination with a modular training strategy, the system demonstrates a significant improvement in overall efficiency, as well as a remarkable ability to adapt to dynamic traffic conditions. The reward system plays a crucial role in this process, ensuring that the agents not only learned to make optimal decisions for the task at hand, but also did so in a way that maintained stability and consistency throughout the training phase; this balance between maximizing performance and ensuring reliable outcomes is key to the robustness of the system.

The comparison between the Tampere and Bari scenarios further underscored the algorithm’s flexibility and ability to generalize across different environments; despite the differences in the two urban settings, the algorithm was able to maintain high levels of performance, demonstrating its reliability under varying conditions. The system’s capacity to adapt to different contexts is particularly important for the practical deployment of autonomous carpooling systems.

Moreover, the comparison with the baseline taxi scenario highlighted the broader impact of intelligent decision-making in shared mobility contexts. While traditional approaches tend to follow static or demand-agnostic routing strategies, the DRL-based system dynamically adapts to passenger demand patterns, leading to more coordinated and context-aware operations. Notably, the adoption of DRL logic also contributed

to a measurable reduction in emissions, aligning the system's performance with increasingly critical environmental sustainability goals—an aspect that reinforces the relevance and timeliness of such intelligent mobility solutions in the context of modern urban planning.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper proposes a hierarchical framework to manage an autonomous carpooling system using DRL techniques. The method uses deep-reinforcement learning to select the best sequence of pick-up and drop-off operations of users and an optimization algorithm optimize the route in the city. The implementation is performed by the Simulation Of Urban Mobility (SUMO) tool to describe the environment and train the agents, and the Traffic Control Interface API to optimize the route. The results demonstrate the potential of the approach for reducing mission times and maintaining high performance across different urban environments.

In detail, the proposed approach shows robust adaptability and generalization capabilities when tested in two European cities, suggesting its suitability for deployment in diverse urban settings. These findings highlight the potential of DRL-based solutions to contribute to more efficient and intelligent urban mobility.

Although the method shows great promise, future work will consider: (i) integration with multi-modal transportation to explore how carpooling can be combined with public transit to enhance overall urban mobility; (ii) improvement of the system interaction with urban environment and its capacity to respond to real-time factors such as traffic lights, congestion, and weather; (iii) investigation of the scalability of the proposed approach to manage a large number of vehicles and passengers; (iv) inclusion of advanced safety features to ensure reliable operation under critical conditions.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Répás, L. Berek, and M. Schmidt, "Autonomous Vehicles Forensics-The next step of the Digital Vehicles Forensics," in *2022 IEEE 1st International Conference on Cognitive Mobility (Cog-Mob)*, Budapest, Hungary, Oct. 2022, pp. 000067–000072. IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CogMob55659.2022.00015>.
- [2] S. S. Shadrin, A. M. Ivanov, and D. A. Makarova, "Methods of Parameter Verification and Scenario Generation During Virtual Testing of Highly Automated and Autonomous Vehicles," in *2022 Intelligent Technologies and Electronic Devices in Vehicle and Road Transport Complex (TIRVED)*, Moscow, Russian Federation, Nov. 2022, pp. 1–6. IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIRVED56074.2022.00001>.
- [3] A. Bienemann and H.-J. Wuensche, "Model Predictive Control for Autonomous Vehicle Following," in *2023 IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium (IV)*, Anchorage, AK, USA, Jun. 2023, pp. 1–6. IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IV51540.2023.00012>.
- [4] X.-Y. Guo and A.-F. Jia, "Study on traffic flow mixed with autonomous vehicles and human-driven vehicles," in *2022 3rd International Conference on Intelligent Design (ICID)*, Xi'an, China, Oct. 2022, pp. 166–171. IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICID55657.2022.00026>.
- [5] S. Hesami, M. Vafaeipour, C. De Cauwer, E. Rombaut, L. Vanhaverbeke, and T. Coosemans, "Proactive Eco-Driving Control of an Autonomous Electric Vehicle in Presence of Signalized Intersections and Preceding Vehicles," in *2023 IEEE Vehicle Power and Propulsion Conference (VPPC)*, Milan, Italy, Oct. 2023, pp. 1–6. IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/VPPC55258.2023.00023>.
- [6] Y. Li, J. Tang, H. Zhao, and R. Luo, "Reinforcement Learning Method with Dynamic Learning Rate for Real-Time Route Guidance Based on SUMO," in *2022 17th International Conference on Control, Automation, Robotics and Vision (ICARCV)*, Singapore, Dec. 2022, pp. 820–824. IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICARCV55331.2022.00056>.
- [7] Y. Ruotong, J. Yao, and L. Qian, "Research on Optimization of Car-hailing Driving Route based on Short-term Traffic Speed," in *2021 6th International Conference on Inventive Computation Technologies (ICICT)*, Coimbatore, India, Jan. 2021, pp. 1017–1024. IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICICT51255.2021.00031>.
- [8] Z. Wang, "Research on the Optimal Route Recommendation Algorithm System for Automatic Driving by Computer Artificial Intelligence Technology," in *2022 IEEE 2nd International Conference on Data Science and Computer Application (ICDSCA)*, Dalian, China, Oct. 2022, pp. 1396–1400. IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICDSCA55658.2022.00051>.
- [9] S. Jain, N. J. Ahuja, P. Srikanth, K. V. Bhadane, B. Nagaiah, A. Kumar, and C. Konstantinou, "Blockchain and Autonomous Vehicles: Recent Advances and Future Directions," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 130264–130328, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3074229>.
- [10] F. Wang, Y. Zhu, F. Wang, J. Liu, X. Ma, and X. Fan, "Car4Pac: Last Mile Parcel Delivery Through Intelligent Car Trip Sharing," *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, vol. 21, no. 10, pp. 4410–4424, Oct. 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ITITS.2020.2984374>.
- [11] K. Poornimathi, A. D. Kumar, and A. Srinithi, "ROUTESENSE – An AI Powered Solution to Car Pooling Systems," in *2024 10th International Conference on Communication and Signal Processing (ICCSIP)*, Melmaruvathur, India, Apr. 2024, pp. 1168–1174. IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCSIP56512.2024.00034>.
- [12] S. Sharma, A. L. Pais, A. Raj, G. Naikrane, and H. Swathi, "Cabverse: An Efficient and Secure Car Pooling System Using Blockchain Technology," in *2023 7th International Conference On Computing, Communication, Control And Automation (ICCUBEA)*, Pune, India, Aug. 2023, pp. 1–5. IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCUBEA58933.2023.10391258>.
- [13] S.-C. Huang, M.-K. Jiau, and C.-H. Lin, "A Genetic-Algorithm-Based Approach to Solve Carpool Service Problems in Cloud Computing," *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 1–5, 2015.
- [14] D. Xiao, X. Yang, and B. Li, "Deep Learning-Based Dynamic Path Planning and Optimization for Autonomous Vehicles," in *2024 4th International Conference on Artificial Intelligence, Robotics, and Communication (ICAIRC)*, Xiamen, China, 2024, pp. 609–612. IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICAIRC64177.2024.10900266>.
- [15] H. Liu, Y. Gu, X. Li, and X. Xiao, "Deep Reinforcement Learning Integrated RRT Algorithm for Path Planning," in *2023 WRC Symposium on Advanced Robotics and Automation (WRC SARA)*, Beijing, China, 2023, pp. 239–244. IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/WRC SARA60131.2023.10261849>.
- [16] I.-M. Tabakis and M. Dasygenis, "Deep Reinforcement Learning-Based Path Planning for Dynamic and Heterogeneous Environments," in *2024 Panhellenic Conference on Electronics and Telecommunications (PACET)*, Thessaloniki, Greece, 2024, pp. 1–4. IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/PACET60398.2024.10496999>.
- [17] Z. Zhou, "Adaptive Control Method for Driverless Cars Considering Probabilistic Graph Path Planning for Intelligent Vehicles," in *2023 3rd International Conference on Mobile Networks and Wireless Communications (ICMNWC)*, Tumkur, India, Dec. 2023, pp. 1–11. IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICMNWC59825.2023.00019>.
- [18] E. Soroka and S. Lall, "Designing a Hardware-Agnostic Interface Between Route and Trajectory Planning in Self-Driving Cars," in *2022 IEEE Conference on Control Technology and Applications (CCTA)*, Trieste, Italy, Aug. 2022, pp. 528–533. IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CCTA56123.2022.00023>.
- [19] S. M. Alam, S. F. A. Rehan, and N. Ahmed, "Optimized Route Planner Application," in *2017 IEEE Region 10 Humanitarian Technology Conference (R10-HTC)*, Dhaka, Bangladesh, Dec. 2017, pp. 125–129. IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/R10HTC.2017.00045>.
- [20] S. Malik, H. A. Khattak, Z. Ameer, U. Shoaib, H. T. Rauf, and H. Song, "Proactive Scheduling and Resource Management for Connected Autonomous Vehicles: A Data Science Perspective," *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 21, no. 22, pp. 25151–25160, Nov. 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1109/JSEN.2021.3086786>.
- [21] E. Neidhardt and D. Suske, "Route Planning Based on Street Criteria for Autonomous Driving Vehicles," in *2021 5th International Conference on Vision, Image and Signal Processing (ICVISIP)*, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, Dec. 2021, pp. 45–48. IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICVISIP55876.2021.00014>.

- [22] J. Tomić, N. Gazivoda, M. Kušljević, P. Sovilj, and M. Šaš, "Travel Route Planning in Smart Cities," in *2023 Zooming Innovation in Consumer Technologies Conference (ZINC)*, Novi Sad, Serbia, May 2023, pp. 88–92. IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ZINC52356.2023.00025>.
- [23] R. Iacobucci, R. Bruno, and J.-D. Schmoecker, "Investigating the Impact of Ride Sharing on the Performance of One-Way Car-Sharing Systems," in *2020 IEEE 23rd International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITSC)*, Rhodes, Greece, 2020, pp. 1–7. IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ITSC45102.2020.9294533>.
- [24] H. J. Vishnukumar, B. Butting, C. Muller, and E. Sax, "Machine Learning and Deep Neural Network — Artificial Intelligence Core for Lab and Real-World Test and Validation for ADAS and Autonomous Vehicles: AI for Efficient and Quality Test and Validation," in *2017 Intelligent Systems Conference (IntelliSys)*, London, UK, 2017, pp. 714–721. IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IntelliSys.2017.8324372>.
- [25] M. Anas, G. C, and K. G, "Machine Learning Based Personality Classification for Carpooling Application," in *2023 International Conference on Intelligent Systems for Communication, IoT and Security (ICISCoIS)*, Coimbatore, India, 2023, pp. 77–82. IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICISCoIS56541.2023.10100353>.
- [26] J. Bezerra and R. Adla, "Machine Learning in Connected Vehicle Environments," in *2023 Congress in Computer Science, Computer Engineering, and Applied Computing (CSCE)*, Las Vegas, NV, USA, 2023, pp. 2536–2540. IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CSCE60160.2023.00407>.
- [27] Z. Meng, "Optimization Path Planning Algorithm Based on Deep Reinforcement Learning," in *2024 Asia-Pacific Conference on Software Engineering, Social Network Analysis and Intelligent Computing (SSAIC)*, New Delhi, India, 2024, pp. 872–876. IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/SSAIC61213.2024.00176>.
- [28] V. Raj and D. Sharma, "Predictive Maintenance in Autonomous Vehicles Using Machine Learning Techniques," in *2024 2nd International Conference on Advances in Computation, Communication and Information Technology (ICAICCT)*, Faridabad, India, 2024, pp. 912–917. IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICAICCT64383.2024.10912235>.
- [29] Tseng, Ying-Tsu, and Huei-Wen Ferng. "An Improved Traffic Rerouting Strategy Using Real-Time Traffic Information and Decisive Weights." *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 70, no. 10, Oct. 2021, pp. 9741–9751. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TVT.2021.3102706>.
- [30] Sutton, Richard S., e Andrew Barto. Reinforcement Learning: An Introduction. Nachdruck. Adaptive Computation and Machine Learning. Cambridge, Massachusetts: The MIT Press, 2014.
- [31] Sharma, Rishabh, and Prateek Garg. "Optimizing Autonomous Driving with Advanced Reinforcement Learning: Evaluating DQN and PPO." In *2024 5th International Conference on Smart Electronics and Communication (ICOSEC)*, pp. 910–914. Trichy, India: IEEE, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICOSEC61587.2024.10722344>.
- [32] Liang, Eric, Richard Liaw, Philipp Moritz, Robert Nishihara, Roy Fox, Ken Goldberg, Joseph E. Gonzalez, Michael I. Jordan, and Ion Stoica. "RLlib: Abstractions for Distributed Reinforcement Learning." *arXiv preprint arXiv:1712.09381*, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1712.09381>.
- [33] Automatic Routing - SUMO Documentation [Online]. Available at: https://sumo.dlr.de/docs/Demand/Automatic_Routing.html (Accessed: 2 May 2025).